

Research article

The phenomenon of *neg1* omission/retention – A regional analysis using the *Atlas linguistique de la France* –

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Abstract: In this study, we analyzed the tendencies in the omission and retention of pre-verbal negative adverb (*neg1*) using the *Atlas linguistique de la France*. The analysis focused on 631 points and 11 maps, conducting statistical analyses from two perspectives: regionality (five linguistic regions) and map type (=morphosyntactic perspective). In the French-speaking regions, *neg1* tended to be retained in peripheral areas, while variability in the omission/retention of *neg1* was observed around Paris. In the Occitan-speaking regions, except for Gascony, there was a strong tendency for *neg1* to be omitted. In the Francoprovençal-speaking regions, *neg1* tended to be omitted in Aosta, Italy, and Valais, Switzerland, but it was generally retained in other areas. In the Catalan-speaking regions, *neg1* was typically omitted, while in the Ligurian-speaking region, *neg1* was retained. However, no statistically significant differences were found between linguistic regions and the omission/retention of *neg1*. On the other hand, statistically significant differences were observed regarding map type. It was found that *neg1* was more likely to be retained when the subject was a determiner phrase (DP) or a proper noun, and more likely to be omitted in constructions like *moi je* [disjunctive form + subject pronoun]. Moreover, in modern spoken French, *ne* tends to be retained when the subject is *nous* or *vous*, whereas this tendency was not observed in negative sentences where the map names included *nous* or *vous*. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the personal pronouns used in the responses obtained from the dialect surveys do not necessarily match those used in the map names. These findings suggest that the morphosyntax of negative sentences has a greater influence on the omission/retention of *neg1* than regionality.

Keywords: *Atlas linguistique de la France*; negation; dialectology; morphosyntax; regional study

1. Introduction

In modern French, negative sentences are expressed by combining the negative particle *ne* with a negative adverb as in (1)b. The negative adverb is also known as *forclusif*, with the most common being *pas*. However, depending on the dialect, different words may be used as negative adverbs. According to Seimiya (2021), who conducted a dialectometrical classification of dialectal points using maps of negative sentences from the *Atlas linguistique de la France* (*ALF*), in addition to the standard

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pas, negative adverbs like *mie* in the east of France, *point* in the north and west of France, *cap* and *brique* in some parts of the south of France, and *nin* in Belgium are used. There are also variations in the meaning of negation depending on the negative adverb, such as *ne...plus* “no longer” and *ne...jamais* “never.”

In spoken language, especially in informal conversations, *ne* is often omitted as in (1)b'. Many sociolinguistic studies, including Ashby (1976, 1981), Coveney (2002), and morphosyntactic studies like Pollock (1989) and Rowlett (1998), have been conducted on the omission of *ne*. From a sociolinguistic perspective, social backgrounds such as age, gender, and place of origin influence the omission of *ne* (Ashby 1976, 1981, 2001; Armstrong and Smith 2002; Coveney 2002). From a morphosyntactic perspective, the type of subject and the content to the right and left of *ne* affect its omission (Ashby 1981; Hansen and Malderez 2004; Meisner and Pomino 2014; Meisner, Tissot and Stark 2015; Moreau 1986).

- (1) a. Je chante.
 I sing.IND.PRS.1SG
 “I sing”
- b. Je ne chante pas.
 I NEG1 sing.IND.PRS.1SG NEG2
 “I do not sing.”
- b'. Je chante pas
 I sing.IND.PRS.1SG NEG2
 “I do not sing.”

In this study, we analyze the omission of negative particle in *ALF*. Section 5.1 briefly outlines the atlas employed in this research, highlighting that the gender and age of the respondents vary depending on the dialectal points. While sociolinguistic analysis is feasible from the perspective of language standardization processes, other forms of analysis may encounter difficulties due to the inherent variability of the data. Nevertheless, because the dialect surveys utilize consistent survey items, it is possible to conduct a geolinguistic analysis from a morphosyntactic perspective. It should be noted that dialect forms do not necessarily use the same word as the standard French *ne*. Therefore, words derived from Latin *non* are referred to as *neg1* for the purpose of analysis. However, when referring to standard French or spoken French, *ne* will be used.

2. Features of the omission of *ne* in spoken French from a morphosyntactic perspective

Regarding the relationship between the omission of *ne* and morphosyntax, Meisner and Pomino (2014) provide a detailed analysis based on prior research. They argue that the subject used in a sentence and its phonological form are related to the omission or retention of *ne*. Subjects that tend to facilitate the omission of *ne* include first-person singular, second-person singular, third-person singular and plural pronouns (*je*, *tu*, *il* and *ils*), indefinite pronouns *on*, and cases where a strong form is simultaneously used like *moi je* (Meisner, Robert-Tissot & Stark 2015). On the other hand, *ne* is more likely to be retained with first-person plural and second-person plural pronouns (*nous* and *vous*), determiner phrases (DP), and proper nouns.

Additionally, they note that even with the same pronoun, the likelihood of *ne* omission varies depending on its pronunciation. For instance, they analyze the relationship between the first-person singular subject pronoun *je* and its four phonetic variants in relation to *ne* omission. When *je* is pronounced as [ʒ], [ʃ], or is omitted (∅), *ne* is completely omitted. However, when pronounced as [ʒə], the degree of omission varies depending on the its left and right elements. Their table summarizes the syntactic structures related to *ne* omission and retention. Negative sentences are more likely to omit *ne* if they correspond to the structures under OMISSION, and more likely to retain *ne* if they correspond to the syntactic structures listed under RETENTION.

Table 1 Morphosyntactic Features of *ne* Omission/Retention¹

	OMISSION	RETENTION
Ashby (1981)	Lexicalization Dependent clause Indicative mood	Non-lexicalization Independent clause Subjunctive mood
Hansen & Malderez (2004) Moreau (1986)	Auxiliary verb Compound tense form	Lexical verb
Armstrong & Smith (2002) Ashby (1981)	Other proclitics	No other proclitics

However, there are some ambiguities concerning the relation between the pronunciation of the subject and the retention of *ne*. For instance, while they state that *ne* is more likely to be retained when *je* is pronounced as [ʒə], it is unclear whether this pronunciation influences the retention of *ne* or if *ne* influences its pronunciation as [ʒə].

¹ Adapted from Meisner & Pomino (2014:25).

Therefore, in this study, we consider the type of subject and the syntactic structure of negative sentences but do not take into account the pronunciation of the subject.

3. Previous studies on negative sentences using *ALF*

There are many previous studies using maps of negative sentence from *ALF*, most of which focus on the types of forclusif. Notable among these are Burnett (2019), Dagnac (2015), and Schwegler (1986).

Burnett (2019) analyzes the types and tendencies of forclusifs used in 22 negative sentences at 150 locations within *ALF*, targeting a total of word 2,989 forms. The survey covers points 1 to 199, including northeastern France, Swiss Romandy, and parts of the Walloon region. In the studied areas, *pas* was predominantly used in the south, *point* and its variant *pont* in the southeast, *mie* in the northwest, and *nen* in the Walloon region (Burnett 2019: 194). Among these forclusifs, *pas* was the most dominant, followed by *mie*, *point/pont*, and *nen*.

Dagnac (2015) analyzes the forclusifs used in Picard dialect using Picartext, *ALF*, and *Atlas linguistique et ethnographique picard*. Some *ALF* maps beyond Picardy were also analyzed. While it is unclear whether all *ALF* negative sentence maps were analyzed, *point* was used in Picardy, its variant *pon* in Artois and much of the Pas-de-Calais department, *nin* in parts of the Nord department, and *pas* and its variant *po* in areas where these three regions intersect.

Schwegler (1986), in his paper on the etymology of *cabdorn*, analyzes Map 89 – *dans ce pays, il n'y a pas de sources* “In this country, there is no source” – in limited regions. He plots on a map the dialectal points in southwestern France where *cap* is used as a forclusif. *cap* was frequently used as a forclusif in the departments of Ariège, Pyrénées-Orientales, and Aude.

In contrast, few studies focus on the omission of neg1. Jagueneau (2007) uses 10 *ALF* negative sentence maps as part of his study on the ratio of neg1 omission/retention in the Limousin dialect. He analyzes 1,040 forms from 104 points centered on the Limousin dialect, stating that in Limousin, neg1 is frequently retained, while in surrounding areas, neg1 tends to be omitted.

Moreover, comprehensive studies on *ALF* as a whole are scarce. Seimiya (2021), in his dialectometrical study, uses 9 maps of negative sentences from *ALF* to explore what kind of matrices should be used to reflect the usage and tendencies of both neg1 omission/retention and types of forclusifs used. Interpretation maps for each map are included in the appendix, providing insights into the regionality of neg1 omission/retention and the forclusifs used.

4. Research questions

There are numerous sociolinguistic and morphosyntactic studies on the omission/retention of *ne* in modern spoken French. By comparing the results of various regional spoken language studies, it is clear that there is a certain degree of regionality in the tendencies of *ne* omission/retention. However, due to the heterogeneous quality of the corpora, a complete comparison seems impossible.

Therefore, by using the negative sentence maps in the *ALF*, it is possible to homogeneously analyze the tendencies of *ne* or neg1 omission/retention throughout France. Based on this, this study set the following two research questions:

1. Are there regional tendencies in the neg1 omission/retention?
2. Based on the results of the first question, are there any maps (= negative sentences) where the neg1 is more likely to be omitted/retained?

5. Methods

This chapter describes the analysis targets and methods.

5.1. Targets

5.1.1. Atlas linguistique de la France

This study uses the *ALF* by Jules Gilliéron and Edmond Edmont for analyzing the neg1 omission/retention in negative sentences. *ALF* is dialect data from the early 20th century, collected between 1897 and 1901. The dialect survey was conducted by Edmont alone, ensuring high reliability when comparing the collected data (Kawaguchi et al. 2021). It includes not only France but also the Franco-Romance regions of Belgium, Switzerland, and Italy, as well as the British Crown Dependencies of the Channel Islands, with a total of 638 points². *ALF* covers five major linguistic regions: Langue d'oïl, Langue d'oc, Francoprovençal, Catalan, and Ligurian. The age range of the subjects is broad, from teenagers to those in their 80s, with the most common being in their 50s, followed by those in their 40s and 60s.

² Although it is often considered as 639 points because two individuals were surveyed at point 284, this study regards it as 638 points.

5.1.2. Maps

There are 19 maps of negative sentences³ in *ALF* (Burnett 2019). These include not only *ne...pas* “not” but also *ne...plus* “no longer” and *ne...ni* “neither...nor.” Among them, this study analyzes the neg1 omission/retention in *ne...pas*. However, maps were excluded if they met the following two conditions:

Condition 1: Maps surveyed only in part of *ALF*

Condition 2: Negation of infinitive verb

Condition 1 was set to conduct quantitative classification in this study. For example, Map 1650 – *je n’ai pas osé le lui dire* “I didn’t dare tell him” – was surveyed in only half of the *ALF* points. Similarly, Map 10 – *n’aie pas peur* “don’t be afraid” – was not surveyed in Nord, Somme, Oise, Aisne, Ardennes, or Marne. Including these maps in the analysis could affect the final statistical analysis due to varying numbers of surveyed maps per dialectal point.

Condition 2 is because this study focuses on negative sentences of finite verb. Therefore, Maps 898-1 – *pour ne pas nous* “so that we don’t” – and 898-2 – *pour ne pas* “so as not to” – were excluded. Furthermore, Map 896-2 – *ne...pas* “not” – was excluded because infinitives are often used depending on the dialectal point. The 11 maps ultimately chosen to be analyzed in this study are listed below, along with the full sentences where only part of the sentence is mapped⁴.

Map 12AB – *moi je ne les aide pas*

Ils	feront		ce qu’	ils	voudront ;
they	do.IND.FUT.3PL		REL.ACC.	they	want.IND.FUT.3PL
moi	je	ne	les	aide	pas.
me	I	NEG1	them	help.IND.PRS.1SG	NEG2

“They will do what they want; I do not help them.”

Map 89 – *il n’y a pas de*

Dans	ce	pays,			
in	this	country,			
il	n’	y	a	pas	de sources.
PRONEXPL	NEG1	there	have.IND.PRS.3SG	NEG2	source

“In this country, there is no source.”

³ There are 19 maps, but a single map may contain multiple negative sentences, resulting in a total of 22 types of negative sentences being surveyed in the dialects.

⁴ For instance, *Ils feront ce qu’ils voudront; moi je ne les aide pas* is divided into four maps: Map 532 – *ils feront*, Map 205 – *ce qu’ils*, Map 1418 – *voudront*, and Map 12AB – *moi je ne les aide pas*.

Map 806AB – si nous ne mangeons pas nos prunes
 si nous ne mangeons pas nos prunes,
 if we NEG1 eat.IND.PRS.1PL NEG2 our plums
 elles se moisiront bientôt
 they go mouldy.IND.FUT.3PL soon
 “If we do not eat our plums, they will soon rot”

Map 817AB – pourquoi ne vous mariez-vous pas ?
 pourquoi ne vous mariez-vous pas ?
 why NEG1 get married.IND.PRS.2PL NEG2
 “Why don’t you get married?”

Map 896-1 – ne...pas
 le roseau plie mais ne rompt pas.
 the reed bend.IND.PRS.3SG but NEG1 break.IND.PRS.3SG NEG2
 “The reed bends but does not break.”

Map 897 – qu’ils ne...pas
 J’ ai cru qu’ ils ne viendraient pas.
 I believe.IND.PST.1SG that they NEG1 come.COND.PRS.3PL NEG2
 “I thought that they would not come.”

Map 899 – n’est pas encore
 le blé est mûr,
 the wheat be.IND.PRS.3SG ripe
 mais l’ avoine n’ est pas encore mûre.
 but the oat NEG1 be.IND.PRS.3SG NEG2 still ripe
 “The wheat is ripe, but the oats are not yet ripe.”

Map 1082 – je ne peux pas
 je ne peux pas perdre,
 I NEG1 can.IND.PRS.1SG NEG2 lose.INF
 ça c’ est sûr.
 it that be.IND.PRS.3SG sure
 “I can not lose, that is for sure.”

Map 1083 – on ne peut pas

Par ce temps, on ne peut pas dormir.
 by this weather one NEG1 can.IND.PRS.3SG NEG2 sleep.INF

“In this weather, one cannot sleep.”

Map 1352 – mais il ne vaut pas

Celui-ci, il est bon,
 this one it be.IND.PRS.3SG good
 mais il ne vaut pas le mien.
 but it NEG1 be worth.IND.PRS.3SG NEG2 mine

“This one is good, but it is not as good as mine.”

Map 1409AB – tu ne vois donc pas

Tu ne vois donc pas que
 you NEG1 see.IND.PRS.2SG so NEG2 that
 tu es aussi vieux que moi.
 you be.IND.PRS.2SG also old that me

“Don’t you see that you are as old as I am.”

5.1.3. Points

After selecting the maps for analysis, the word forms of each point at each map were entered into Excel. Of the 638 points in *ALF*, 7 points (261, 281, 282, 291, 396, 874, 989) had missing word forms in at least one map. To facilitate statistical analysis, these 7 points were excluded, resulting in 631 points analyzed in this study. ShinyDialect was used to create the interpretation maps of this study.

Fig. 1 Distribution of 631 points and language boundary⁵

5.2. Methods

5.2.1. Digitization of map data⁶

The word forms corresponding to standard French *ne* and *pas* on the selected 11 maps were entered into Excel. There were no major issues with the word forms corresponding to the forclusif, *pas*. However, some word forms that were presumed to correspond to *ne* were difficult to judge as negative adverb or other elements at first glance.

For example, in Map 89, the word form ‘*dy*’ in ‘*dy o pa de*’ at point 614 and the word form ‘*d*’ in ‘*d a pa de*’ at point 969, and the word form ‘*d*’ in ‘*k i d ... ñ*’ at point 291

⁵ The language boundary lines adopted are those from the SYMILA project at Université Toulouse-II-Jean-Jaurès and Goebel (2018).

⁶ The actual word form in alphabet Rousselot-Gilliéron is written in italic within ‘’.

in Map 897 were challenging. Only when it was difficult to judge based on the target map alone were other maps referred to as needed.

The word forms ‘*dy*’ at point 614 and ‘*d*’ at point 969 in Map 89 were judged not to be negative adverbs based on word forms of *il y a* (there is/are) being confirmed in Maps 103 – *il y a eu* “there was/were” – and 729 – *il y a huit jours* “a week ago” –. On the other hand, the word form ‘*d*’ at point 291 in Map 897 could not be considered anything other than *ne* based on other maps. ‘*d*’ in *ALF* phonetically represents a voiced alveolar plosive [d], similar to the alveolar nasal [n], except for the characteristic that the air does not pass through the nasal cavity. Thus, this ‘*d*’ at this point was judged to be *ne* not pronounced nasally for some reason. Additionally, ‘*j én*’ at point 261 in Map 12 was judged to be a miswritten ‘*jé n*’ based on the first-person singular form ‘*jé*’ in Maps 1082 – *je ne peux pas* “I cannot” – and 1084 – *je...pouvais* “I could” –, and ‘*én*’ was treated as *ne*.

If a negative sentence was constructed using only *neg1* without *forclusif*, it was treated as a point retaining *neg1*.

5.2.2. Analysis of regionality of *neg1* retention/omission

The number of maps on which *neg1* was retained out of the 11 maps was counted for each point. Points where *neg1* was never retained were labeled as *n0*, and those where *neg1* was retained on all maps were labeled as *n11*, creating a 12-stage labeling system based on the number of times *neg1* was retained. An interpretation map was then created for the *neg1* omission/retention in the 11 maps, analyzing the regionality of *neg1* omission/retention. To analyze whether the tendency of *neg1* omission/retention varies by language region, a two-way ANOVA was conducted. The statistical software R4.3.1 was used for the analysis.

5.2.3. Analysis of maps of *neg1* retention/omission

After clarifying the regionality of *neg1* omission/retention, statistical analysis was conducted on points excluding *n0* and *n11*. By excluding *n0*, where *neg1* was always omitted, and *n11*, where *neg1* was always retained, it was judged that it would be possible to identify maps that were more prone to omitting *neg1* or vice versa. To analyze whether the tendency of *neg1* omission/retention varies by map (=type of negative sentence), Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted. The same statistical software was used for the analysis.

6. Results

First, in section 6.1, the distribution of neg1 omission/retention in the interpretation maps of the 11 analyzed maps is presented and briefly analyzed. Then, in sections 6.2 and 6.3, the tendencies of neg1 omission/retention are analyzed from two perspectives: regionality and the type of negative sentence.

6.1. Brief analysis of each map

The distribution of neg1 omission/retention in the 11 analyzed maps is presented. Interpretation maps are color-coded with blue for $-neg1$ points (=omission) and red for $+neg1$ points (retention).

6.1.1. Map 12

Fig. 2 neg1 omission/retention of Map 12

In Map 12, there are 426 *-neg1* points (68%) and 205 *+neg1* points (32%), with more points where *neg1* is omitted. This map has the most *-neg1* points among the analyzed maps. One notable feature of this map is that it is the only map where disjunctive pronoun, the strong form, of a first-person pronoun, is included in the map title. Even in areas where subject pronouns are omitted in other maps, the subject pronoun or the disjunctive form is used in this map.

According to Meisner et al. (2015), in modern spoken French, when the subject combines a disjunctive subject with a subject pronoun like *moi je*, *ne* is more likely to be omitted. Although this data is from about 100 years ago, this map also shows a prominent omission of *neg1*, indicating a similar tendency.

6.1.2. Map 89

Fig. 3 *neg1* omission/retention of Map 89

In this map, there are 377 *-neg1* points (60%) and 254 *+neg1* points (40%), with more points where *neg1* is omitted. This map has the second-highest number of *-neg1*

points among the analyzed maps. In Ashby (1981), it is stated that in lexicalized expressions such as *il y a* “there is/are,” *ne* is more likely to be omitted, showing a similar tendency to modern spoken French.

6.1.3. Map 806

Fig. 4 neg1 omission/retention of Map 806

This is a map where the first-person plural pronoun *nous* is used. In modern spoken French, *nous* is generally used in formal settings where *ne* tends to be retained. However, in this map, there are 323 +neg1 points (51%) and 308 –neg1 points (49%), with a slight predominance of +neg1.

Looking closely at the subject pronouns, *nous* was used in only 137 points, about 20% of the total. The most common was pro-drop with 219 points, followed by *je* in 218 points. An indefinite pronoun *on* widely used instead of *nous* in modern spoken French, was used in 55 points. The contracted form *nous autres* was used in only 2 points.

Table 2 summarizes the subject types and neg1 omission/retention. In pro-drop points, neg1 is more likely to be omitted, while *on* and *nous* as subjects tend to retain neg1. When the subject is the first-person singular *je*, there is no significant difference, but there are more points retaining neg1.

Table N Subject Type and neg1 omission/retention in Map 806

	<i>je</i>	<i>on</i>	<i>nous</i>	<i>nous autres</i>	∅	Total
-neg1	99	4	44	1	160	308
+neg1	119	51	93	1	59	323
Total	218	55	137	2	219	631

6.1.4. Map 817

Map 817 is the only map of negative interrogative, with the second-person plural pronoun as the subject. There are 341 +neg1 points (54%) and 290 -neg1 points (46%).

Question sentences with interrogatives can have two syntactic structures: [interrogative + V + S] and [interrogative + S + V]. Therefore, the map title *pourquoi ne vous mariez-vous pas?* can also be understood as *pourquoi vous ne vous mariez pas?* In the latter case, the subject pronoun *vous* moves to the left of *ne*, which is not the case in the former.

The table summarizes the syntactic structures and neg1 omission/retention in the 631 analyzed points. Regardless of the word order, neg1 is retained twice as much, and subject inversion does not seem to affect neg1 omission/retention. However, in points where the subject is omitted, neg1 is more likely to be omitted. Over 80% of the points with subject omission are in the Occitan-speaking regions.

Table 3 Syntactic Structure and neg1 omission/retention in Map 817

	int + S + V	int + V + S	int + V	total
-neg	71	70	149	290
+neg	153	141	47	341
total	224	221	196	631

6.1.5. Map 896

This map uses the neg1 in a coordinate clause introduced by the conjunction *mais* “but,” with the same subject, leading to subject omission in the coordinate clause. There are 436 +neg1 points (69%) and 195 -neg1 points (31%), making it the map with the second-highest number of +neg1 points. The distribution shows that in the French-speaking regions, almost all points retain neg1, while in the Occitan-speaking regions, neg1 is omitted in most points.

Fig. 6 neg1 omission/retention of Map 896

6.1.6. Map 897

Map 897 is the only map using the third-person plural pronoun. The entire sentence is *j'ai cru qu'ils ne viendraient pas*, with the negative sentence in the subordinate clause and the verb in the present conditional tense, which is significantly different from other maps. There are 416 +neg1 points (66%) and 315 -neg1 points (34%). In the French-speaking regions, neg1 tends to be retained overall, despite some areas around Poitou where neg1 is omitted. In contrast, in the Occitan-speaking regions, neg1 is omitted in almost all points.

Fig. 7 neg1 omission/retention of Map 897

6.1.7. Map 899

This map includes a negative sentence in a coordinate clause introduced by the conjunction *mais* “but,” but with a different subject in the coordinate clause compared to Map 896. There are 491 +neg1 points (78%) and 140 -neg1 points (22%), making it the map with the highest number of +neg1 locations. Unlike other maps, even in the Occitan-speaking regions, which typically sees neg1 omission, especially in the east, neg1 is retained.

Fig. 8 neg1 omission/retention of Map 899

6.1.8. Map 1082

The negative sentence itself is *je ne peux pas perdre*, but the dialect survey was conducted with the phrase *je ne peux pas perdre, ça c'est sûr*. There are 361 +neg1 points (57%) and 270 –neg1 points (43%).

In modern spoken French, *ne* is generally more likely to be omitted with the first-person singular subject *je*, but this is not necessarily the case in this map. The fact that the verb is *pouvoir* “can” would also be a reason for retention of neg1. In written language, *pouvoir* can form negative sentences without neg2. Indeed, some points formed negative sentences using only neg1. Additionally, the complexity of the right elements, *ça c'est sûr*, may have created an environment where neg1 is more likely to be retained.

Fig. 9 neg1 omission/retention of Map 1082

6.1.9. Map 1083

This is the only map using the indefinite pronoun *on* as the subject. There are 418 +neg1 points (66%) and 213 -neg1 points (34%). Even in the Occitan and Francoprovençal-speaking regions, which typically see neg1 omission, some locations retain neg1. Particularly in the Occitan-speaking region, the indefinite pronoun *on* is used. According to Ronjat (1937: §774), personal pronouns are not usually used in Occitan, and they are used to avoid ambiguity or for contrast. In most maps analyzed, except for Map 12 and Map 1083, personal pronouns were not used in the Occitan-speaking regions. This suggests that the presence or absence of personal pronouns affects the omission/retention of neg1 in the Occitan-speaking regions.

Fig. 10 neg1 omission/retention of Map 1083

6.1.10. Map 1352

This map uses a negative adverb in a coordinate clause introduced by the conjunction *mais* “but.” There are 374 +neg1 points (59%) and 257 –neg1 points (41%). While previous maps of negative sentences in the coordinate clause (Map 896 and Map 899) had many +neg1 points (436 points and 491 points respectively), this map shows different tendencies. Unlike the previous two maps, which had nouns as subjects, this map uses pronouns, indicating that this difference may influence neg1 retention.

Fig. 11 neg1 omission/retention of Map 1352

6.1.11. Map 1409

This is the only map using the second-person singular pronoun. There are 393 +neg1 points (59%) and 258 -neg1 points (41%), with more +neg1 points. The negative sentence is in the main clause leading the subordinate clause *que tu es aussi vieux que moi*. Ashby (1981) states that *ne* is more likely to be omitted in main clauses, but this is not necessarily the case in this map. Instead, as Meisner et al. (2014) mention, the complexity of the right elements of neg1 seems to influence neg1 retention.

Fig. 12 neg1 omission/retention of Map 1409

6.2. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention in the entire ALF area

6.2.1. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention by regionality

Figure 13 shows the interpretation map of the number of neg1 retentions in the 11 maps. The double lines in the figure indicate language boundaries. Points where neg1 is omitted/retained in more than 70% of the maps (n0~n3 and n8~n11) are summarized in a single legend.

From the figure, regional tendencies in the omission/retention of neg1 can be observed. In the Occitan-speaking regions (excluding Gascony), the Catalan-speaking regions, the Francoprovençal-speaking regions of Valais in Switzerland and Aosta in Italy, n0~n3 are prevalent. Conversely, in the northern French-speaking regions (including the northwest and northeast), around the Croissant area, excluding the aforementioned regions, in the Francoprovençal-speaking regions, Gascony in the Occitan-speaking regions, and the Ligurian-speaking region, n8~n11 are more common.

Furthermore, many n5 and n6, where the omission/retention of neg1 is about half and half, are distributed between regions with strong tendencies to retain or omit neg1. There are 330 points where neg1 is omitted in more than 70% of the maps (n0~n3), 207 points where neg1 is retained in more than 70% of the maps (n8~n11), and 94 intermediate points (n4~n7). The breakdown of each language region is as shown in Table 4.

	n0	n1	n2	n3	n4	n5	n6	n7	n8	n9	n10	n11
no	73	64	49	21	24	23	24	23	37	87	94	112
%	11.5	10	8	3	4	3.5	4	3.5	6	14	15	17.5

Fig. 13 Summary of neg1 omission/retention in 11 maps

Table 4 Number of Points Classified into n0~n3, n4~n7 and n8~11 in each Language Region

	<i>ALF</i>	French	Occitan	Francoprovençal	Catalan	Ligurian
n0~n3	207	44	145	13	5	0
n4~n7	94	62	43	10	0	0
n8~n11	330	236	22	50	0	1
total	631	342	210	73	5	1

A two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) was conducted to investigate the relationship between the overall tendencies of neg1 omission/retention and language regions. Factor (A) was the tendency of neg1 omission (three levels), and Factor (B) was the number of language regions (five regions). The results are shown in Table 5. The p-value for Factor (A) = $0.467 > 0.05$, indicating no significant difference in the tendency of neg1 omission/retention. The p-value for Factor (B) = $0.162 > 0.05$, also indicating no significant difference in the tendency of language regions. Thus, there is no significant relationship between language regions and the overall tendency of neg1 omission/retention.

Table 5 Result of two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$)

	variation	df	variance	F-value	p-value	decision
Factor (A)	5572.9	2	2786.5	0.84	0.467	[]
Factor (B)	28928.9	4	7232.2	2.18	0.162	[]
Error	26583.1	8	3322.9			

6.2. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention by map

Table 6 summarizes the number (and percentage) of points where neg1 was retained and omitted in each map. Maps 12 and 89 have over 60% of points where neg1 was omitted. Conversely, maps 896, 897, 899, and 1352 have over 60% of points where neg1 was retained. Maps 1082, 1352, and 1409 have more points retaining neg1, while maps 806 and 817 have about half and half.

To identify maps where neg1 is more likely to be retained or omitted, the analysis focused on points classified as n1~n10, excluding n0 and n11. For example, 64 points are classified as n1. If these 64 points retained neg1 only on specific maps, those maps could be considered more likely to retain neg1.

Table 6 Number and Percentage of neg1 Omission/Retention in each Map

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409
+neg1	205 (32)	254 (40)	323 (51)	341 (54)	436 (69)	416 (66)	491 (78)	361 (57)	418 (66)	374 (59)	373 (59)
-neg1	426 (68)	377 (60)	308 (49)	290 (46)	195 (31)	215 (34)	140 (22)	270 (43)	213 (34)	257 (41)	258 (41)

Table 7 summarizes the relationship between points where neg1 was retained (n1~n10) and the maps where neg1 was retained. The bottom row shows the number of points retaining neg1 excluding the number of n11 points. Row n1, for example, shows the maps where the 64 points classified as n1 retained neg1. For instance, 31 out of 64 points retained neg1 in Map 899, 16 in Map 1083, etc. Column 12 shows the composition of points retaining neg1 in Map 12. Of the 93 points, 30 are classified as n9, and 49 as n10.

Table 7 Number of Points Classed into n1~n10 in each Map: entire ALF

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409	total
n1	0	2	2	0	9	4	31	0	16	0	0	64
n2	0	7	3	1	12	9	40	1	19	0	6	49
n3	0	0	3	3	15	12	15	3	5	3	4	21
n4	1	3	3	7	17	16	20	6	15	6	2	24
n5	1	6	6	6	21	19	18	10	12	7	9	23
n6	3	8	4	14	21	20	20	10	14	15	15	24
n7	5	6	9	13	21	17	22	16	14	20	18	23
n8	4	12	21	23	33	35	36	30	34	35	33	37
n9	30	31	73	72	81	82	85	79	85	84	81	87
n10	49	67	87	90	94	90	92	93	92	92	93	94
total	93	142	211	229	324	304	379	249	306	262	261	

Figure 14 is a box plot based on Table 7, showing the distribution of neg1 retention of points classed in n1~n10 for each map. From the table and figure, it is clear that Map 12 has notably fewer points retaining neg1. Similarly, Map 89 also has relatively few points retaining neg1. On the other hand, Maps 896, 897, 899, and 1083 show higher medians, indicating more points retaining neg1. To verify whether the differences in neg1 retention tendencies between maps are statistically significant, a hypothesis test was conducted with the following null hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis: The tendency of neg1 retention is unrelated to the type of map.

Fig. 14 Box Plot of Number of n1~n10 Points in each Map: entire ALF

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted for all combinations of maps at a significance level of 1%. The results are shown in Table 8. Bold indicates p-values < 0.01, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis for those combinations. For example, Map 12 shows significant differences with all maps except Map 1352, indicating that Map 12 tends to omit neg1 more than other maps except Map 1352.

Table 8 Results of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (p-values < 0.01): entire ALF⁷

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409
12											
89	0.009										
806	0.006	0.27									
817	0.009	0.05	0.139								
896	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006							
897	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.009	0.036						
899	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.137	0.015					
1082	0.009	0.047	0.024	0.174	0.006	0.012	0.008				
1083	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.009	0.356	0.959	0.014	0.019			
1352	0.014	0.047	0.05	0.076	0.036	0.058	0.009	0.201	0.154		
1409	0.009	0.032	0.022	0.057	0.014	0.032	0.008	0.16	0.111	0.725	

To visually clarify the results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, the significant differences were converted to 0-1 data⁸, and hierarchical clustering (complete linkage, Manhattan distance) was performed. The 11 maps can be broadly divided into two groups based on statistical significance. The box plot and dendrogram are compared to analyze these two groups.

⁷ All values were rounded to the fourth decimal place. The same applies to all subsequent analyses.

⁸ P-values < 0.01 were marked as 1, and p-values > 0.01 were marked as 0. The same applies to all subsequent analyses.

The first group includes Maps 12, 896, 897, 899, and 1083. This group contains maps with strong tendencies for neg1 omission and retention. Among the 11 maps, Map 12

Fig. 15 Result of hierarchical clustering of 11 maps: 631 points

showed the most significant differences, with statistical significance against all maps except Map 1352. Therefore, Map 12 tends to omit neg1 more than other maps except Map 1352. The next most significant differences were seen in Map 899, showing statistical significance against seven maps. This indicates that Map 899 tends to retain neg1. Maps 896, 897, and 1083 are also statistically significant in retaining neg1 but do not show statistical significance with Map 899, indicating that these three maps are also less likely to omit neg1.

The second group includes Maps 89, 806, 817, 1082, 1352, and 1409. Among these, Maps 89, 806, and 817 show statistical significance with the maps in the first group, indicating that they tend to retain neg1

compared to Map 12 and tend to omit neg1 compared to Maps 896, 897, 899, and 1083. Maps 1082, 1352, and 1409 show statistical significance with three or fewer maps, indicating that these three maps do not have a strong tendency to omit or retain neg1.

6.3. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention by language region

In 6.2, it was clarified that Map 12 tends to omit neg1, while Maps 896, 897, 899, and 1083 tend to retain neg1. To validate these results, similar analyses were conducted for each language region except for Catalan and Ligurian.

6.3.1. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention in the French-speaking regions

Of the 342 points in the French-speaking regions, 236 points (70%) are classified as n8 or higher, indicating a strong tendency to retain neg1. Points with a strong tendency to omit neg1 (n3 or lower) are 44 points (12%), mainly distributed in Poitevin, Berrichon, and Bourbonnais. Points with a wide variation in neg1 retention/omission

(n4~n7) are 62 points (18%). Table 9 summarizes the relationship between points retaining neg1 (n1~n10) and the maps where neg1 was retained in the French-speaking regions. Figure 16 is a box plot based on Table 9.

Table 9 Number of Points Classed into n1~n10 in each Map:
342 Points in French-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409	total
n1	0	0	1	0	7	2	2	0	0	0	0	12
n2	0	0	3	0	7	3	10	1	1	0	5	15
n3	0	0	2	3	14	6	10	1	2	2	2	14
n4	0	1	2	5	14	10	13	4	8	3	0	15
n5	1	3	4	3	15	14	14	9	11	3	8	17
n6	0	4	2	11	17	14	14	7	14	9	10	17
n7	0	1	6	9	13	9	13	11	7	10	12	13
n8	2	7	16	17	26	27	26	20	24	26	25	27
n9	15	17	52	52	60	59	59	56	60	59	60	61
n10	32	43	60	64	64	60	64	64	64	62	63	64

Fig. 16 Box Plot of Number of n1~n10 Points in each Map: 342 Points in French-speaking regions

In the French-speaking regions, Maps 12 and 89 tend to omit neg1 more than other maps. Maps 896 and 899, consistent with the analysis in section 6.2, tend to retain neg1 in the French-speaking regions. Maps 897 and 1083, which showed a tendency to retain neg1 in section 6.2, do not necessarily show this tendency in the French-speaking regions. Table 10 shows the results of statistical hypothesis tests. Bold indicates p-values < 0.01, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 10 Results of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (p-values < 0.01):
342 Points in French-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409
12											
89	0.022										
806	0.006	0.021									
817	0.014	0.022	0.187								
896	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.009							
897	0.002	0.002	0.014	0.043	0.01						
899	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.009	0.125	0.056					
1082	0.009	0.009	0.035	0.399	0.009	0.041	0.009				
1083	0.009	0.009	0.038	0.068	0.014	0.135	0.021	0.121			
1352	0.014	0.022	0.122	1	0.009	0.044	0.014	0.952	0.206		
1409	0.014	0.013	0.028	0.232	0.009	0.22	0.012	0.23	0.799	0.201	

The significant differences were converted to 0-1 data, and hierarchical clustering

Fig. 17 Result of hierarchical clustering of 11 maps:
342 points in French-speaking region

(complete linkage, Manhattan distance) was performed. The 11 maps can be broadly divided into three groups based on statistical significance. The first group includes Maps 896 and 899. Map 896 shows significant differences with five maps, and Map 899 with six maps. These two maps tend to retain *neg1* in the French-speaking regions, consistent with the overall analysis. The second group includes Maps 12 and 89. Map 12 shows significant differences with six maps, and Map 89 with five maps, indicating that Maps 12 and 89 tend to omit *neg1*. The third group includes the remaining seven maps. Among these, Maps 897 and 1083, which showed a tendency to retain *neg1* in the analysis in 6.2, are included.

6.3.2. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention in the Occitan-speaking regions

Of the 210 points in the Occitan-speaking regions, 145 points (69%) are classified as n3 or lower, indicating a strong tendency to omit neg1. Points with a strong tendency to retain neg1 (n8 or higher) are 43 points (21%), and points with wide variation in neg1 omission/retention (n4~n7) are 22 points (10%). Most n4 or higher points are distributed in Limousin, Marchois, and Gascon.

Table 11 summarizes the relationship between points retaining neg1 (n1~n10) and the maps where neg1 was retained in the Occitan-speaking regions. Figure 18 is a box plot based on Table 11.

Table 11 Number of Points Classed into n1~n10 in each Map:
210 Points in Occitan-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409	total
n1	0	2	1	0	2	2	24	0	13	0	0	44
n2	0	7	0	1	3	5	28	0	17	0	1	31
n3	0	0	1	0	1	6	5	2	3	1	2	7
n4	1	2	1	1	3	5	6	2	7	3	1	8
n5	0	3	2	3	5	4	3	1	1	3	0	5
n6	2	4	0	2	3	3	4	1	0	3	2	4
n7	2	4	1	2	4	3	5	3	5	5	1	5
n8	1	0	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2
n9	6	10	14	14	15	13	16	14	15	16	11	16
n10	8	12	15	14	16	16	16	16	15	16	16	16

Fig. 18 Box Plot of Number of n1~n10 Points in each Map: 210 Points in Occitan-speaking regions

In the Occitan-speaking regions, the distribution of neg1 omission/retention varies significantly from the French-speaking regions. This is due to the higher prevalence of neg2 in the Occitan-speaking regions. From the box plot, it is clear that Map 12 tends to omit neg1, while Map 899 tends to retain neg1. Map 1083 also shows a tendency to

retain neg1. To verify the statistical significance of the differences in neg1 omission/retention by map, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted for all combinations of maps at a significance level of 1%. Table 12 shows the results of the statistical hypothesis tests. Bold indicates p-values < 0.01, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 12 Results of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (p-values < 0.01):
210 Points in Occitan-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409
12											
89	0.015										
806	0.178	0.644									
817	0.058	0.72	0.588								
896	0.009	0.228	0.019	0.01							
897	0.009	0.151	0.024	0.03	0.524						
899	0.006	0.014	0.009	0.014	0.042	0.054					
1082	0.037	1	0.24	0.665	0.053	0.042	0.014				
1083	0.014	0.059	0.042	0.075	0.312	0.645	0.029	0.076			
1352	0.014	0.55	0.05	0.049	0.395	0.397	0.059	0.066	0.4		
1409	0.136	0.356	0.774	0.526	0.024	0.013	0.009	0.188	0.045	0.076	

Fig. 19 Result of hierarchical clustering of 11 maps:
210 points in Occitan-speaking regions

The significant differences were converted to 0-1 data, and hierarchical clustering (complete linkage, Manhattan distance) was performed. The 11 maps can be broadly divided into three groups based on statistical significance. The first group includes Map 899. Map 899 shows significant differences with Maps 12, 806, and 1409, which tend to omit neg1. Of the 44 points classified as n1 in the Occitan-speaking regions, 24 retained neg1, and of the 31 points classified as n2, 28 retained neg1, indicating that Map 899 tends to retain neg1. The second group includes Map 12. Map 12 shows significant differences with

Maps 896, 897, and 899, which tend to retain neg1. The box plot distribution shows that Map 12 has very few points retaining neg1, indicating that it tends to omit neg1. The third group includes the remaining nine maps. Among these, Maps 806 and 1409 show significant differences with Map 899, indicating that they tend to omit neg1 compared to Map 899. Maps 896 and 897 show significant differences with Map 12, indicating that they tend to retain neg1 compared to Map 12. However, considering the overall 11 maps, these four maps do not have a strong tendency to omit or retain neg1.

6.3.3. Analysis of neg1 omission/retention in the Francoprovençal-speaking regions

Of the 73 points in the Francoprovençal-speaking regions, 50 points (69%) are classified as n8 or higher, indicating a strong tendency to retain neg1. Points with a strong tendency to omit neg1 (n3 or lower) are 13 points (18%), and points with wide variation in neg1 omission/retention (n4~n7) are 22 points (13%). Points with a strong tendency to omit neg1 are mainly distributed in isolated mountainous areas like Valais in Switzerland and Aosta in Italy.

Table 13 summarizes the relationship between points retaining neg1 (n1~n10) and the maps where neg1 was retained in the Francoprovençal-speaking regions. Figure 20 is a box plot based on Table 13.

Table 13 Number of Points Classed into n1~n10 in each Map:
73 Points in Francoprovençal-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409	total
ne1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	0	0	6
ne2	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
ne3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ne4	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
ne5	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
ne6	1	0	2	1	1	3	2	2	0	3	3	3
ne7	3	1	2	2	4	5	4	2	2	5	5	5
ne8	1	5	3	4	6	7	8	8	8	7	7	8
ne9	9	4	7	6	6	10	10	9	10	9	10	9
ne10	9	12	12	12	14	14	12	14	13	14	14	14

Fig. 20 Box Plot of Number of n1~n10 Points in each Map:
73 Points in Francoprovençal speaking regions

Unlike the French-speaking and Occitan-speaking regions, the Francoprovençal-speaking regions shows less variation in neg1 omission/retention by map. Nonetheless, Map 12, similar to the other regions, tends to omit neg1 more than other maps. To verify the statistical significance of the differences in neg1 omission/retention by map, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted for all combinations of maps at a significance level of 1%. Table X shows the results of the statistical hypothesis tests. Bold indicates p-values < 0.01, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 14 Results of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (p-values < 0.01):
73 Points in Francoprovençal-speaking regions

	12	89	806	817	896	897	899	1082	1083	1352	1409
12											
89	1										
806	0.586	0.462									
817	0.679	0.203	1								
896	0.206	0.021	0.103	0.066							
897	0.013	0.014	0.013	0.022	0.106						
899	0.007	0.014	0.022	0.021	0.232	1					
1082	0.269	0.058	0.174	0.136	0.915	0.071	0.168				
1083	0.203	0.058	0.223	0.202	0.943	0.222	0.056	1			
1352	0.058	0.036	0.035	0.04	0.341	0.149	0.608	0.345	0.546		
1409	0.021	0.022	0.021	0.035	0.242	1	1	0.12	0.301	0.346	

Statistical significance was only observed between Maps 12 and 899. Map 12 tends to omit neg1 compared to Map 899, and Map 899 tends to retain neg1 compared to Map 12. However, compared to the French-speaking and Occitan-speaking regions, there is little difference in the tendencies of neg1 omission/retention by map in the Francoprovençal-speaking regions.

6.4. Summary of the analysis

The analysis revealed that Map 12 tends to omit neg1, while Map 899 tends to retain neg1. In the French-speaking regions, Map 89 also tends to omit neg1, and Map 896 tends to retain neg1, which is a characteristic specific to the French-speaking regions. In the analysis of the entire *ALF* area, Maps 897 and 1083 also showed statistical tendencies to retain neg1, but this is not necessarily the case in the analysis by each language region. These maps are relatively more likely to retain neg1, in the context of *ALF* as whole.

The regional analysis and map analysis indicated that Map 12, the only map using the strong form of the first-person pronoun, *moi*, has the strongest tendency to omit neg1. This tendency is consistent with Meisner et al.'s (2015) findings that strong forms lead to neg1 omission even in *ALF*, data from the early 20th century. Similarly, Map 899 showed a tendency to retain neg1 when the subject position is occupied by a proper noun or nouns other than personal pronoun.

Table 15 Summary of neg1 omission/retention

	<i>ALF</i>	French	Occitan	Francoprovençal
12	-neg1	-neg1	-neg1	-neg1
89		-neg1		
806				
817				
896	+neg1	+neg1		
897	+neg1			
899	+neg1	+neg1	+neg1	+neg1
1082				
1083	+neg1			
1352				
1409				

7. Conclusion

In this study, we analyzed the retention rate of *neg1* for each map to elucidate whether there are regions where *neg1* tends to omit/retain and whether there are negative sentences where *neg1* tends to omit/retain. To this end, we conducted an analysis of 11 maps of negative sentences from the *ALF*.

The findings indicate that in the Occitan-speaking regions, excluding Gascony, the Catalan-speaking regions, the Francoprovençal-speaking regions of the Valais in Switzerland, and the Aosta Valley in Italy, there were numerous instances where *neg1* was omitted. Conversely, in the northern French-speaking regions (particularly in the northwest and northeast), around the Croissant area, the Occitan-speaking regions of Gascony, and the Ligurian-speaking region, there were many instances where *neg1* was retained. However, no statistically significant differences were observed in the retention/omission of *neg1* when considered as language regions, and it became evident that there is variability even within a single language region.

The analysis of each map revealed that the omission of *neg1* was statistically prominent in maps where the disjunctive forms were used, whereas the retention of *neg1* was prominent in maps where proper nouns were employed. In maps where *nous* and *vous*, which are generally considered to easily retain *neg1*, were the subjects, no statistically significant differences in the retention of *neg1* were observed. However, this may be attributed to discrepancies between the map names and the forms that emerged in the actual dialect surveys. Thus, it can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between the subject and the omission/retention of *neg1*, as evidenced from the linguistic maps.

Abbreviations

Atlas

ALF

Atlas linguistique de la France

Gloss

ACC

accusative

COND

conditional

FUT

future

IND

indicative

INF

infinitive

NEG

negative

NEG1

pre-verbal negative

NEG2

post-verbal negative

PRONEXPL

impersonal pronoun

PRS

present

PL	plural
REL	relative
SG	singular
Other	
–neg1	neg1 omission
+neg1	neg1 retention

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